

Research Paper

Acidification of animal slurry in housing and during storage to reduce NH₃ and GHG emissions-recent advancements and future perspectives

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Slurry acidification
Livestock housing
Manure storage
NH₃ emissions
GHG emissions

ABSTRACT

Ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions are an environmental issue associated with animal manure management. Concrete, practical, and economic solutions are needed for farmers and other stakeholders around the globe to solve this issue. Decreasing slurry pH with the help of acids or other compounds is a well-documented technique to reduce ammonia and methane emissions from slurry. However, the effect of manure acidification on N₂O emissions is still not clear. Recently, acidifying agents other than the previously used mineral acids have been tested such as e.g. organic acids, bio-waste materials, and microbial inoculations. However, the effectiveness of these acidifying agents in reducing the slurry pH and mitigation of gaseous emissions further needs to be reviewed. Also, the effectiveness of acidification in combination with other manure treatments such as composting, solid-liquid separation, and anaerobic digestion requires consideration in whole-system solutions. Here, recent studies have been compiled and reviewed to determine the applicability of acidification options for slurry management to deepen our understanding of the environmental impact of slurry acidification. The literature review revealed that temperature fluctuations have a substantial impact on the acidified slurry's performance during storage. A viable substitute for conventional mineral acids could be organic acids and biomaterials like sugars whey, and microbes. Furthermore, apple pulp, sugar beet molasses, and grass silage are examples of bio-waste products that exhibit promise as acidifying agents. However, to gain a better understanding of the viability and usefulness of the recently evaluated acidifying compounds, more research is still required.

1. Introduction

Animal manure is a substantial source of ammonia (NH₃) and greenhouse gases (GHG) such as methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Le Riche et al., 2016; Sokolov et al., 2019). At global level, Asia and South America are the main contributors of GHG from the livestock sector (Fig. 1). NH₃ is a poisonous gas that is dangerous to human health and an indirect source of N₂O, whereas both CH₄ and N₂O are gases that contribute to global warming and climate change (Jayasundara et al., 2016; Sokolov et al., 2019). Fig. 2 shows the global NH₃ emissions from manure management, highlighting some of the European and Asian countries as a major contributors. Furthermore, NH₃ emitted into the

atmosphere precipitates in the soil, which leads to soil acidification and results in biodiversity loss and alteration in the composition of plant species (Guthrie et al., 2018). Agriculture is responsible for 32% of the world's anthropogenic CH₄ emissions and 81% of the NH₃ emissions, and reducing these emissions in agriculture can help achieve the Paris Agreement's targets (Kuylensstierna et al., 2021; UNEP, 2021; Van Damme et al., 2021; Wyrer et al., 2022). To keep the global warming below 1.5°C the emissions must peak before 2025 and should decline by 43% by 2030.

The European Union (EU) pledged to reduce NH₃ emissions by 19% starting in 2030 as part of the updated NEC Directive (Directive, 2016). 19 EU members may fail to meet these goals, according to the European

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2025.114856>

Received 18 November 2024; Received in revised form 19 March 2025; Accepted 28 April 2025

Available online 5 May 2025

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Environment Agency (EEA) [EEA \(2019\)](#). According to data from 2021, there has been a 13% worldwide decrease in NH₃ emissions since 2005, with 16 nations having achieved their targets and 10 remaining in need of additional reductions. Except for Austria, Ireland, Latvia, and Luxembourg, the majority of EU nations reported reductions in NH₃ emissions as of 2023. To fulfill the 2030 targets, eight countries must reduce their emissions by 10–30% ([EEA, 2023](#)). Since NH₃ emission reductions are occurring more slowly than those of other pollutants, achieving these reductions is still quite difficult. By 2030, Germany specifically aims to reduce its NH₃ emissions by 29% from 2005 levels ([Directive, 2016](#)). An analysis of the currently available NH₃ mitigation techniques in Germany was carried out by [Häussermann et al. \(2018\)](#) and based on their findings currently available mitigation techniques (see e.g. [Amon et al., 2021](#)) will not be able to reduce NH₃ emissions to the targeted level. They reported a maximum of 26.9% reduction with the current mitigation measures. It shows that there is a need to induct new effective measures to meet the target emission reductions within the assigned time frame not only in Germany, but in all EU member states.

In animal production systems, slurry (urine, faeces) is removed from the animal house and often stored outside in steel or concrete tanks or silos, or in lined earth-banked lagoons. Tanks tend to have smaller surface area per unit volume as compared to lagoons. Significant volumes of GHG (31%) and almost all of NH₃ are released into the atmosphere during manure management in the EU 28 ([Mohankumar Sajeev et al., 2018](#); [UNECE, 2016](#); [UNFCCC, 2016](#)).

Therefore, it is imperative to develop cost-effective methods for reducing NH₃ and GHG emissions from manure storage to lessen the effects of livestock production on the environment. Acidification could

reduce emissions by 65–95% from cattle and pig slurry being stored for about three months ([Habtewold et al., 2018](#); [Petersen et al., 2014, 2012](#)). According to the Danish Ministry of Environment, Danish law supports this technology ([Hjorth et al., 2015](#)). In Denmark, 20% of all the slurry is acidified before field application ([Jensen et al., 2018](#); [Pedersen et al., 2022](#)). A discrete choice experiment was conducted in Germany in which 129 German livestock farmers took part. The results showed that the majority of the farmers (80.6%) will opt for this technology if it is available through support schemes ([Thiermann and Latacz-Lohmann, 2022](#)). They also suggested that the German government should follow the Danish government to implement this technology.

Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the effect of slurry acidification on NH₃ and GHG emissions during storage. In these studies, emissions reduction varied between 40 and 85% for NH₃ and 68 and 96% for GHG ([Kavanagh et al., 2019](#); [Sokolov et al., 2019](#); [Sommer et al., 2017](#); [Wang et al., 2023](#)). This variability in emission reduction by slurry acidification could depend on experimental conditions, type of acid, amount of acid, and slurry type, and composition. Commercial slurry acidification solutions have primarily focused on slurry storage and to some extent on slurry in pits beneath animal housing, but it is also common and less expensive to acidify slurry in storage tanks before field application.

Various acids can be used to acidify slurry ([Eriksen et al., 2012](#); [Regueiro et al., 2016b](#)), while sulphuric acid is typically the most used for acidification of slurry ([Fangueiro et al., 2015](#)). Compared to other acids, H₂SO₄ has lower acidification costs ([Iria et al., 2013](#); [Overmeyer et al., 2021](#)). However, the use of H₂SO₄ can result in an excess of sulphur fertilization during land applications ([Bittman et al., 2014](#)). In

Global CH₄ emissions from livestock systems

Global N₂O emissions from livestock systems

Fig. 1. Global GHG emissions from the livestock sector in 2021 (FAOSTAT <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/>, accessed on 02 September 2024).

addition, hydrogen sulphide and unpleasant smells may be produced (Bittman et al., 2014; Dai and Blanes-Vidal, 2013; Joubin et al., 2018) and its use requires special safety requirements. Furthermore, certain types of concrete may develop gypsum when exposed to high sulphate concentrations in an acidified slurry (Locher, 1977). This could be a problem for the storage tanks made up of concrete. Due to these drawbacks, other acids (acetic acid, etc.) that are just as effective as sulphuric acid must be taken into consideration. It would also be possible to use other slurry or storage treatments (e.g., solid-liquid separation, anaerobic digestion) to reduce the sulphuric acid level (Overmeyer et al., 2021). However, care should be taken when using acidified slurry for anaerobic digestion because acidified slurry (>10% of total slurry volume) in biogas plants can reduce biogas production as it inhibits the microbial activity (Moset et al., 2012; Regueiro et al., 2022).

Since organic acids tend to be weak, large quantities are required to achieve the desired pH level (Bittman et al., 2014) depending on the slurry type and composition. According to Overmeyer et al. (2021) 16–17% less H₂SO₄ was required to achieve the desired pH (5.5) of fattening pig and sow slurry as compared to organic acids. While in the case of dairy slurry the amount of H₂SO₄ required was higher (13–45%) as compared to organic acids.

Additionally, it is believed that organic acids may break down more quickly, which could result in foam formation and the emission of carbon dioxide (Bittman et al., 2014; Overmeyer et al., 2021). However, they might present an opportunity, particularly for organic farming, as they might be more easily accepted for the acidification of slurry than sulphuric acid (Joubin et al., 2018). It is also possible to use easily degradable organic compounds like sucrose, glucose, sugar beet residues, or brewing sugar in place of adding acids to the slurry because the fermentation of these products results in the formation of organic acids, which in turn causes the pH value to decrease (Bastami et al., 2016; Clemens et al., 2002). In terms of degradability Regueiro et al. (2022) showed that addition of 2% glucose to pig slurry significantly reduced the initial pH (5.7) through conversion to lactic acid. Added glucose was completely converted to lactic acid in 14 days following further two weeks for degradation of lactic acid.

Manure acidification is currently one of the hot topics of discussion among scientists, researchers, and policymakers because of its remarkable effectiveness in reducing the gaseous emissions from manure. Currently, several researchers are working on this particular topic to evaluate the effectiveness of different acidic agents in reducing manure

pH. From our understanding, a comprehensive review on this topic was last published by Fangueiro et al. (2015) where they reviewed the effect of different acids on slurry pH, the role of acidification in the fertilizer value of slurry, and the effect on NH₃, CO₂ emissions and also discussed briefly about CH₄ emissions. Since then, a significant number of additional papers have been published on this topic. Fangueiro et al. (2015) summarised studies on manure acidification and almost all of them were based on chemical acidic agents e.g., H₂SO₄ and salts. In recent research, several researchers also evaluated the effectiveness of organic or bio-based materials in reducing slurry pH. To better understand the current status and the recent progress in this technique, a review of the latest research papers is required. This review aims to highlight the recent research related to the acidification of manure/slurry in animal housing and during the storage period, to review the effectiveness of different acidic agents (chemical, organic, bio-based) in reducing the pH of manure/slurry under different conditions and to highlight the shortcomings in research related to manure/slurry acidification including suggestions for the future research.

2. Methodology

To carry out this review, a literature search was conducted by using the Web of Science (<https://webofknowledge.com/>) and SCOPUS® databases (<http://www.scopus.com>). The following keywords and their combinations were used: “Acidification”, “slurry”, “manure”, “digestate”, “liquid manure”, “storage”, “barn”, “housing”, “ammonia emissions”, “greenhouse gas emissions” and all their potential abbreviations. Boolean operators e.g., OR, AND, and the Boolean truncation “*” were used to improve the search results. Only articles published in English were selected from different countries around the globe. The process of studies selection is shown in the PRISMA Flow Diagram (Fig. 3a).

The literature search resulted in 365 studies in total and after limiting the search from 2015 to 2025, 250 studies were obtained. After that, the duplicate studies (n = 69) were removed which left 181 studies for screening. Title, abstract and full text screening was followed, leaving 74 relevant studies. These 74 studies include research articles, review papers, conference papers and book chapters addressing slurry acidification in livestock house or during slurry storage.

Research articles published in or after 2015 were used to extract relevant data such as slurry type, scale of experiment, acids/acidifying agents used, slurry dry matter, dose of acids, initial and final pH of slurry

Fig. 2. Global NH₃ emissions from manure management in 2022 (Data Source: EDGAR; <https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu>; accessed on 16.09.2024).

Fig. 3. (a) Step by step process of selection of studies (b) overview of studies published from 2015 to 2025 focusing on emission reduction from livestock manure.

and the mitigation percentage of NH_3 and GHG which is presented in Tables 1 and 2. Emission reduction percentage of NH_3 and CH_4 was calculated for different acids/acidifying agents for cattle and pig slurry keeping in mind the study scale. For this purpose, the mitigation percentages by slurry acidification as compared to control treatments given in the studies were extracted and averaged. For the studies where only mean emissions from acidified and control slurries were given, the emission reduction percentage was calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{Emission mitigation}(\%) = \frac{\text{mean emission}(\text{control}) - \text{mean emission}(\text{treatment})}{\text{mean emission}(\text{control})} \times 100$$

In addition, the relationship between the H_2SO_4 dosage and pH of slurry was calculated by keeping in mind the type of slurry (pig slurry & cattle slurry). The result is presented in Fig. 7a in the later part of this review. Furthermore, the relationship of slurry pH and temperature with NH_3 emission reduction was calculated for cattle slurry (Fig. 7b). A similar relationship for pig slurry was not included because of the large variation in terms of pH and temperature with emission reduction. Data points from manure storage were considered because there were only few data points from housing studies.

In addition, a literature search was conducted by using the SCOPUS® database to get an overview of studies published focusing on NH_3 and GHG emission reduction from livestock manure. We obtained 884 research, review articles and book chapters. The overview is presented in Fig. 3b and showed that since 2020 there is an increasing trend in the articles focusing on emission reduction from livestock manure by using different manure management practices.

3. Mechanism of action of acids and the methodology of slurry acidification

3.1. Acidic/acidifying agents and their mechanism of action

There are different acidic/acidifying agents which have been tested

for slurry acidification. Based on the existing literature we can categorize these acidic/acidifying agents into:

- i. Mineral acids (i.e., H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , HCl)
- ii. Organic acids (Acetic acid, lactic acid, citric acid, phosphoric acid, etc.)
- iii. Sugars (Glucose, Sucrose, brewing sugar, etc.)
- iv. Bio waste (Grass silage, apple pulp, sugar beet molasses, etc.)
- v. Salts (CaCl_2 , FeCl_2 , FeCl_3 , AlCl_3 , alum)
- vi. Other organic compounds

Several acids/acidifying agents have been tested for manure acidification. Out of these, H_2SO_4 is the most commonly used (Im et al., 2020). The different mineral acids have a similar mechanism of reducing the pH and consequently the emissions. More specifically, the addition of acids to any medium that has a higher pH resulted in the dissociation of acids. This process of dissociation resulted in the release of protons and ultimately reduced the pH of the medium. Strong acids dissociate completely which leads to a higher reduction in pH as compared to weak acids which do not dissociate completely. Similarly, the addition of any type of acid to the animal slurry which usually has a higher pH resulted in acid dissociation which then reduced the slurry pH. However, maintaining the lower pH for a longer period of time depends on the buffer capacity of the slurry which controls the acid degradation. The complex buffering capacity of the slurry is primarily determined by the amounts of volatile fatty acids, carbonates, phosphates, and ammonical N (Sommer and Husted, 1995). An increase in the pH of pre-acidified slurry was observed in previous studies attributed to microbial oxidation of dissociated acids releasing hydroxyl ions (Regueiro et al., 2016b; Regueiro et al., 2022). The addition of mineral acids (H_2SO_4) can maintain slurry pH at a lower level for longer as compared to organic acids (acetic or lactic acid) due to slow degradation (Joubin et al., 2018). Decomposition of organic acids could increase the carbonate buffer resulting in a faster increase in pH after acidification as compared to

Table 1
Effect of cattle slurry acidification on NH₃ and GHG emissions in housing and during storage.

Manure type	Study scale	Stage	Acidic/acidifying agents	Storage temp.	Dosage	Dry matter	pH before acidification	Target pH	Storage time	NH ₃	CH ₄	N ₂ O	CO ₂	References
Cattle urine	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	10°C	6.1 L/m ³	3.6%	9.1	5.4	19 days	−82%	−41%	53%		(Mahdi et al., 2025)
Cattle slurry					6.8 L/m ³	7.1%	7.8	5.2		−60%	No diff.	−5%		
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	24°C	1.84 g/L		8.0	7.27	42 days		−36%			(Matos Pereira Lima et al., 2025)
			H ₂ SO ₄		5.23 g/L		8.0	5.44			−65%			
			H ₃ PO ₄		1.69 g/L		8.0	7.37			−19%			
			H ₃ PO ₄		4.79 g/L		8.0	6.37			−54%			
Cattle slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	9°C	NA	6.2%	7.3	5.5	77 days	−32%	−46%			(Owusu-Twum et al., 2024)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ modified vermiculite cover	22°C	5 M H ⁺	NA	8.59	7.62	84 days	−64%				(Wang et al., 2024)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄		NA	NA	NA	NA	24 h	−92%				(Zhang et al., 2021b)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	15°C					38 days	−22%				
Cattle slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	19°C	3 L/m ³	NA	7.2	5.0	241 days	−8%	−95%	–	–	(Lemes et al., 2022)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	20°C	NA	8.5%	8.5	5.5	90 days	−61%	−98%	–	−15%	(Miranda et al., 2021)
Cattle slurry	Outdoor storage tanks	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (95 %)	–	2 g/L	5.10%	8.24	7.4	114 days	−30%	−85% to −89%	−21%	–	(Sokolov et al., 2021)
Cattle slurry	Outdoor storage tanks	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (70 %)	17.6°C	2.4 L/m ³	NA	7.5	6.0	~180 days	−23% to −33%	−38% to −77%	−50% to −73%	–	(Sokolov et al., 2020)
Cattle slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (70 %)	–	2.4 L/L slurry	NA	NA	5.9–6.5	120 days	–	−69 to −84%	–	–	(Habtewold et al., 2018)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	20°C	NA	1.6 g/kg	7.2	5.5	60 days	−62%	−68%	Negligible	–	(Sommer et al., 2017)
Cattle slurry 1	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (98 %)	20°C	NA		6.7	<5.5	24 h	−95%	–	–	–	(Finzi et al., 2019)
Cattle slurry 2							7.2			−89%				
Cattle slurry-cool	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	7.3°C	2.77 L/m ³	NA	7.3	5.5	62 days	−56%	−86%	No significant emissions	−28%	(Misselbrook et al., 2016)
Cattle slurry-Temperate				11°C	5.53 L/m ³		7.1		71 days	−99%	−91%		−3.2%	
Cattle slurry-Warm				17.2°C	3.87 L/m ³		7.3		72 days	−68%	−63%		−31%	
Cattle slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (70 %)	20°C	1.4 mL/L	NA	7.4	6.5	160 days	−41%	−87%			(Sokolov et al., 2019)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ modified vermiculite cover	10°C	2.4 mL/L	NA	7.88	–	77 days	−53%	−89%	−28%	–	(Wang et al., 2021)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ , Alum	15°C	180 meq/kg slurry (H ₂ SO ₄), 165 meq/kg slurry (Alum) 270 meq/kg slurry (H ₂ SO ₄)	54.8 g/kg	7.2	5.5	60 days	−69% to −87%	–	–	–	(Iria Regueiro et al., 2016b)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	–	~20 mL/L	9%	7.2	5.5	11 days	−75%	−89%	–	–	(Fuchs et al., 2021)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	CH ₃ COOH	–	~20 mL/L					−83%	Negligible			
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	8.6°C	2.01 g/g	4% &	7.4 & 7.5	5.5	84 days	−85%	–	–	–	(Kavanagh et al., 2019)
			Acetic acid		4.35 g/g	7%				−73%				
			Ferric chloride		8.25 g/g					−96%				
			Alum		8.85 g/g					−82%				

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Manure type	Study scale	Stage	Acidic/acidifying agents	Storage temp.	Dosage	Dry matter	pH before acidification	Target pH	Storage time	NH ₃	CH ₄	N ₂ O	CO ₂	References
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Alum, FeCl ₂ , Polyaluminium chloride, Biochar	–	NA	10.5%	7.5	5.4–7.3	7 days	–54 to –92%	–99 to –121%	–44 to –63%	–	(Brennan et al., 2015)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Brewing Sugar, Activated EM	30°C	10 % w/w (brewing sugar) 5 % v/w (activate EM)	10.6% & 11.2%	7.4 & 7.8	<4.5	30 days	–40 to –70%	–75%	–	–	(Bastami et al., 2016)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Whey	20°C	342.73 g/L	NA	7.21	5.5	12 days	–88 to –90%	–	–	–14 to –23%	(Gioelli et al., 2022)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Whey Sugar	26.5°C	0.5 L/kg slurry 40 g/kg slurry	5.46%	7.52	<5.5	60 days	–68% –45%	–	Negligible	–	(Prado et al., 2020)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Sugar beet molasses (5 %) Grass silage (7 %) Apple pulp (7 %) Ferric chloride	10°C	5 % 7 % 7 % 1.1 %	7%	6.4	4.6–6.0	116 days	–67% –38% –49% –20 to –68%	–15 to –70% –6 to –65%	–	–6 to –38%	(Kavanagh et al., 2021)
Cattle slurry	Lab	Storage	Liquid biowastes	38°C	1 Liter/kg slurry	16.9%	7.35	4.94–5.08	180 days	–83.8% to –86.7%	–70% to –77%	–19.5% to –36.9%	–	(Samer et al., 2019)
Cattle slurry	Farm scale	Storage	Acid activated biochar	–	NA	78.7 g/kg	8.3	7.1	82 days	–25 to –28%	–	–	–	(Baral et al., 2023)
Slurry digestate	Lab	Storage	Biochar + H ₂ SO ₄ Biochar + H ₃ PO ₄ Biochar + H ₂ O ₂	5°C	0.5 g/100 g 0.59 g/100 g 0.34 g/100 g	4.06%	8.2	1.55 2.65 4.80	240 days	–95% –88% –80%	–	–	–	(Covali et al., 2021)
Recycle flush water	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	–	–	NA	7.9	4.5	–	–39%	–	–	–	(Neerackal et al., 2017)
Beef feedlot	Lab	Housing	Alum	23°C	10 % (g/g of total mass)	54.5%	7.0	5.9	21 days	–72.3%	–	–62.25%	–4.40%	(Spiehs and Woodbury, 2024)
Cattle slurry	Pilot scale	Housing	Alum H ₂ SO ₄ CaCl ₂	12°C	10 mL/m ² 10 g/m ² 100 mL/m ²	9.8%	8.6	6.0	–	–76% –41% –69%	–	–	–	(McIlroy et al., 2019)

Table 2
Effect of pig slurry acidification on NH₃ and GHG emissions in housing and during storage.

Manure type	Study scale	Stage	Acidic/acidifying agents	Storage temp.	Dosage	Dry matter	pH before acidification	Target pH	Storage time	NH ₃	CH ₄	N ₂ O	CO ₂	References
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	20°C	10 mL/L	NA	7.99	5.5	40 days	−99%	−99%	77%	−59%	(Gómez-Muñoz et al., 2025)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	Brown juice HCl H ₂ SO ₄ HNO ₃ H ₃ PO ₄ CH ₂ O ₂ CH ₃ COOH H ₂ SO ₄		50 % w/w 4.1 L/m ³ 1.3 L/m ³ 3.3 L/m ³ 3.3 L/m ³ 2.3 3.7 L/m ³ NA	NA	7.1	6.8 5.0	180 days	−92% −39% −48% −3.8% −68% −8% −14% −96%	−84%	57%	−41%	(Chen et al., 2024)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (95 %)	4°C	NA	NA	8.6	5.0–6.0	78 days	–	−6% to −23%	–	–	(Ambrose et al., 2024) (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2023)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	Lactic acid (70 %)	26.8°C	NA	NA	7.1	5.5–6.0	43 days	−69–85%	−98%	−29%	–	(Wang et al., 2023)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (95 %)	20°C	8 mL/kg	1.22 %	8.1	5.0	30 days	−58%	No effect	No effect	No effect	(Pereira et al., 2022b)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (95 %)	20°C	8 mL/kg	22.2 g/kg	8.3	5.0	35 days	−49%	−45%	2.45%	−3%	(Pereira et al., 2022a)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (95 %) + temperature decrease	25°C	0.5–1.6 g/L	NA	7.8 & 7.4	6–7	43 days	–	−70%	–	–	(Im et al., 2020)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	30°C	0.7–10.3 g SO ₄ ^{2−} /L	NA	8.4	5–7	40 days	–	+0.4 kg CO ₂ eq./ton pig slurry	–	–	(Shin et al., 2019)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	21°C	NA	NA	7.2	5.5 6.5	~8 days	−92.3% −49.4%	–	–	–	(Park et al., 2015)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	19.5°C	6.1 L/m ³	NA	7.5	5.0	241 days	−67%	−95%	–	–	(Lemes et al., 2022)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	~16°C	1.2–6 kg/m ³	4.2 %	6.7	6.1–6.8	63 days	−33 to −78%	−46 to −96%	–	–	(Ma et al., 2022)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	–	NA	NA	8.55	5.5	8–15 days	–	>−95%	–	–	(Ambrose et al., 2023a)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ , Alum	15°C	NA	15.3 g/kg	7.4	5.5	60 days	−75% to −81%	–	–	–	(Regueiro et al., 2016b)
Pig slurry (Fresh)	Lab	Storage	Alum	25°C	2 %	NA	7.28 7.85	5.5	70 days	Negligible −92%	−81%	–	−48% −54%	(Regueiro et al., 2016c)
Pig slurry (Co-dig.)	Lab	Storage	Tannic acid-Fluoride	21°C	11 g/L	10.03 %	6.55	6.4	12 days	−70% −95%	−91% −99%	–	–	(Dalby et al., 2020)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Manure type	Study scale	Stage	Acidic/acidifying agents	Storage temp.	Dosage	Dry matter	pH before acidification	Target pH	Storage time	NH ₃	CH ₄	N ₂ O	CO ₂	References
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	Self-produced lactic fermentation	21°C	NA	NA	7.34	4.5	90 days	–	–86%	–57%	–	(Cong et al., 2023)
Pig slurry	Lab	Storage	Synthetic lactic acid bacteria community	21°C	NA	NA	8.3	5.0	12 days	–95.5%	–	–	–	(Liu et al., 2023)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	Citric acid	30°C	0.75–12.75 kg/t	NA	7.4	<6.0	35 days	–	–85 to –99%	–	–	(Im et al., 2021)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄	21°C	2.73 L/m ³ slurry	NA	7.41	5.5	65 days	–99%	–92%	–	–99%	(El Bied et al., 2023)
Pig slurry liquid	Lab	Storage	Elemental sulphur	25°C		NA	8.28 7.29	5.7–7.0	60 days	–28%	–89 to –96%	–52 to –91%	–	(Maffia et al., 2020)
Pig slurry 1	Lab	Storage	H ₂ SO ₄ (98 %)	20°C	NA		7.9	<5.5	24 h	–49% –90% –97%	–82%	–	–	(Finzi et al., 2019)
Pig slurry 2	Pilot scale	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄ (96 %)	–	5.1 kg/pig (spring), 5.6 kg/pig (autumn and summer)	8.9 %	6.8	<6.0	–	Summer: –44% Spring: –66% Autumn: –71% –70%	Summer: ND Spring: –50.3% Autumn: ND	Summer: –5.2% Spring: –1.1% Autumn: –2.9%	–	(Petersen et al., 2016)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄	–	0.5 kg/100 L slurry	3.3 %	7.5	<6.0	–	–	–	–	–	(Kai et al., 2008)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄	19–23.2°C	NA	3.9 %	7.1	4.9–5.4	–	–39%	–67%	–	–	(Overmeyer et al., 2023)
Pig slurry	Pilot scale	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄	7–15°C	NA	NA	NA	5.5	–	–	–91 to –93%	–	–	(Vechi et al., 2022)
Raw solid fraction	Lab	Storage	Elemental sulphur (80 %)	20.5°C	2 % w/w	23.4 %	7.14	5.5	30 days	–70%	–	–	–	(Gioelli et al., 2016)
Co-digested solid fraction				21.3°C		26.5 %	7.77		60 days	–65%				
Pig slurry	Lab	Housing	H ₂ SO ₄ HNO ₃	–	11.48 g/kg slurry 19.69 g/kg slurry	9.35 %	7.21	5.5	–	–	–91.5% –99%	–	–	(Dalby et al., 2022)
			Acetate		NA						–55%			

mineral acids (Overmeyer et al., 2021). The amount of acid required to achieve the target pH depends on the complex buffer system of the slurries. Buffer capacity of slurries could be influenced by the temperature, time of storage and the ingredients of the slurry (Overmeyer et al., 2021, 2020). Joubin et al. (2018) reported a lower amount of H_2SO_4 for pig slurry to reach the pH 6.4 ($0.5 L/m^3$) and 6.0 ($1.6 L/m^3$) as compared to cattle slurry ($2.4 L/m^3$ to pH 6.4 & $3.6 L/m^3$ to pH 6.0). This could be due to lower initial pH of pig slurry (6.65) as compared to cattle slurry (7.29) representing the higher buffer capacity of cattle slurry (Regueiro et al., 2016b). Similarly, Overmeyer et al. (2021) reported that over three times more acid was required to achieve the target pH 5.5 of sow slurry as compared to cattle and pig slurries. One reason behind this could be higher initial pH and lower VFAs of sow slurry. Another reason could be the higher TAN content which leads to higher carbonates upon decomposition (Sigurdarson et al., 2018), which creates a stronger carbonate buffer and ultimately required higher amounts of acid. Besides their higher effectiveness, mineral acids have some limitations in their use, such as hazards to living beings, cost-intensiveness, and corrosiveness. (Fangueiro et al., 2015).

Similarly, organic acids such as lactic acid, citric acid, acetic acid, etc. work according to the same mechanism as explained above.

In addition, sugars and bio waste materials such as glucose, whey, apple pulp, sugar beet molasses, etc. are also reported to be used for slurry acidification. These can be converted to organic acids by microorganisms (e.g., endogenous anaerobic microbes) (Eq. (1)) and then follow the above-mentioned reaction (Berg and Pазsiczki, 2006; Fangueiro et al., 2015).

Precipitating salts such as $FeCl_2$, aluminium chloride, and poly ammonium chloride reported to be able to lower the slurry pH (cattle slurry) significantly ranging from 4.6 to 6.0 (Brennan et al., 2015; Kavanagh et al., 2019, 2021). Dissolution of such salts results in the liberation of protons (Eq. (2)) followed by the same acidic reaction as explained above.

The choice of a particular acidifying agent depends on different factors such as the target pH, the type of manure/slurry, the stage of the manure management chain, etc.

Slurry acidification could reduce NH_3 emissions significantly because the pH of slurry has a significant impact on the equilibrium between NH_4^+ , NH_3 , and H^+ . When an acid is added to lower the pH, the equilibrium shifts from the volatile non-ionized form of NH_3 to the non-volatile ionized form of NH_4^+ (Conn et al., 2007; Fangueiro et al., 2013; Arogo et al., 2003; Pedersen et al., 2022) (Eq. (3)). The total amount of NH_3 -nitrogen is present as NH_4^+ at a pH of 6.0 (Fangueiro et al., 2015), which means there would be less chances of NH_3 emission.

On the other hand, the exact mechanism of CH_4 emission reduction is not clear, while it is obvious that the addition of H_2SO_4 and the resulting reduction in pH can affect the microbial communities and the methanogens throughout all the stages of organic matter degradation (Habtewold et al., 2018). In contrast to untreated manure, Habtewold et al. (2018) found no differences in the abundance and activity of bacterial communities in acidified dairy manure but did find a 6% reduction in methanogen abundance and up to 20% decrease in activity. This suggests that rather than other microbial processes, H_2SO_4 disturbs methanogenesis exclusively; nevertheless, further studies are required to corroborate these findings. Petersen et al. (2012) reported that the addition of potassium sulphate ($1.6 g/kg$ slurry equivalent to the S amount required if acidification was done by H_2SO_4) to cattle slurry showed 63–67% inhibition of methanogens with no significant pH reduction. They claimed that methanogenesis is prevented by sulphur transformations without any pH decrease. Therefore, instead of necessarily aiming for a specific manure pH level, lower H_2SO_4 rates could restrict CH_4 generation (Ma et al., 2022). However, it should be kept in mind that the reduction in manure pH could still be required to mitigate the NH_3 emissions. Similarly, 0.1–2% addition of elemental sulphur (80%) to pig raw slurry and separated fractions reduced GHG emissions by 78–79% (Gioelli et al., 2016; Maffia et al., 2020). For further details see Section 5.

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of the acidification process modified from Santonja et al. (2017).

Fig. 5. Variation in buffer capacity with respect to change in pH adapted from (Fangueiro et al., 2015) based on the data from (Sommer and Husted, 1995) (License Number: 5992440412716).

3.2. Methodologies for slurry acidification

Acidification of slurry is mainly carried out at three stages of the manure management chain:

- i. In-house acidification of slurry is a well-known technique for the sustainable management of manure. It is normally considered a long-term acidification process (Fig. 4) (Fangueiro et al., 2015, 2013; Petersen et al., 2012). In this technique, the most common process is to flush the slurry from channels to the treatment tank, where the acid is added to the slurry during continuous mixing to obtain the required pH level (<6.0) and a fraction of the slurry is pumped back to the manure pits where it mixed with the newly produced slurry (Kai et al., 2008; Kupper et al., 2025; Overmeyer et al., 2023; Uvarov et al., 2019). The main issue in this process is the production of foam, which could be avoided by proper aeration (Dalby et al., 2022; Fangueiro et al., 2015).
- ii. Acidification of manure during storage is the most preferred and most researched technique. Similarly to in-house acidification, the acidic agents are added to the storage tank or lagoon during mixing. The main hurdle in this process is the removal of foam (Fangueiro et al., 2015; Kai et al., 2008).
- iii. Slurry acidification at the manure application stage is also a well-established method. In this case, the acid is added to the slurry tank just before application to the soil. It is known as short-term acidification (Fangueiro et al., 2015).

In this review, we mainly focused on slurry acidification at the housing and the manure storage stage.

4. Effect of acidification on slurry composition and processes

Animal slurry is a complex mixture of dissolved and suspended compounds and particles. Changes in the slurry composition occur continuously due to different biological and chemical processes. These processes are affected by the pH of the slurry such as the acid-base pairs in the slurry. According to Fangueiro et al. (2015) and Christensen & Sommer (2013), animal slurry consists of six acid-base pairs and this

speciation of acids and bases depends on the pKa value and ultimately pH-dependent. A detailed procedure for the calculation of acid-base pairs at a specific pH is explained by (Fangueiro et al., 2015).

4.1. Effect of the acidification on the buffer capacity of the slurry

The pH of slurry varies on a time scale after acidification, either in housing or during storage. That is because of the strong buffer capacity of the animal slurry (Fig. 5). Different buffers exist in the animal slurry including the volatile fatty acid buffer (VFA buffer), the $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NH}_3$ buffer, and the $\text{CO}_3^{2-}/\text{HCO}_3^-$ buffer (Overmeyer et al., 2020). The dominance of any of these buffers influences the pH of the slurry or it could be the opposite as the existence of any of these buffers depends on the slurry pH. This characteristic of the animal slurry influences the amount of acid required to achieve a target pH of the slurry. During acidification, the addition of an acid increases that relevant acid buffer and reduces the other existing buffers e.g., CO_3^{2-} buffer (Fangueiro et al., 2015). Apart from the pH, buffer capacity also depends on other parameters of the slurry e.g., slurry temperature. With the increase in temperature the VFA buffer increased at a pH range (of 5.5–3.0) on the other hand at a pH range of (7.0–5.5) CO_3^{2-} increased and the VFA buffer was decreased (Overmeyer et al., 2020; Overmeyer et al., 2021). The fluctuation in different buffer systems with the change in slurry temperature is due to the change in microbial activities (McGill and Jackson, 1977; Overmeyer et al., 2020). This shows that storing the slurry under cool conditions slows down the breakdown and the build-up of the buffer system.

4.2. Effect of slurry acidification on organic matter degradation and microbial population

Generally, in raw slurry, the organic matter (OM) goes through anaerobic degradation and increases the overall emissions from the slurry. There are different microbial groups involved in the degradation of OM in the slurry including methanogenic, acidogenic, hydrolytic, and acetogenic (Fangueiro et al., 2015; Habtewold et al., 2018; Hjorth et al., 2013). All of these microbial groups are sensitive to the pH change. The microbial processes carried out by these groups are inhibited by

lowering the pH. These microbial groups have different levels of pH for their optimum growth e.g., acetogens and the methanogens showed optimum growth at pH around 7.0 while most of the acidogens and the hydrolytic bacteria grow better at pH 6.0 (Angelidaki et al., 2011; Habtwold et al., 2018). However, achieving the optimum pH of 5.5 after acidification does not completely inhibit these microbes, which would require reducing the pH of slurry below 4.0 (Overmeyer et al., 2021). The reduction of volatile solids in the acidified slurries gradually showed that these microbes were still active (Gioelli et al., 2022; Habtwold et al., 2018; Sommer et al., 2017). Reduction of the volatile solids in acidified cattle slurry were 24–27% (storage period 15 days) and 17–18% (storage period 35 days) (Gioelli et al., 2022; Habtwold et al., 2018). It was also reported that at the start of the slurry acidification hydrolysis of carbohydrates and other compounds accelerated, but the process was chemically catalyzed instead of enzymatic reactions (Hjorth et al., 2013). As explained above in Section 3, the acidification of slurry by using H₂SO₄ particularly inhibited the methanogenic community of microbes (Habtwold et al., 2018). Change in the slurry pH can alter the active sites and the steric structures of the enzymes and lead to the inhibition of the activity (Fangueiro et al., 2015). Along with the lower pH, the anaerobic conditions and the lower temperature during storage could delay the OM degradation for a longer period as compared to the aerobic conditions (Overmeyer et al., 2021). This alteration in the OM degradation in the acidified slurry would change the overall composition of the slurry.

Pathogenic microbes such as *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) are one of the major concerns in animal slurries. Applying the slurry with a higher population of *E. coli* to the soil could lead to leaching to the adjacent water bodies and the underground water as well (Michelon et al., 2023). Acidification of slurry could also act as a sanitization technique to reduce the population pathogen below permissible limits. It was reported that the acidification of slurry to pH 5.0, reduced the population of *E. coli* below sensitization limit (Rodrigues et al., 2021). According to previous studies, treatments such as acidification, mechanical

separation, or other additive additions could reduce the environmental impact of the slurry (Owusu-Twum et al., 2017; Soares et al., 2019). Acidification could decrease the population of some of the microbes (i. e., *Methanomicrobiales*, *Methanobacteriales* and *Methanosarcinales*, etc.) while it can increase other specific populations e.g., Lactic acid producing bacteria (LAB) (Assouhoun-Djeni et al., 2016; Bastami et al., 2021). The higher population of the LAB is because of their higher tolerance to acidity and alternatively, it could also explain the higher concentration of lactic acid in the acidified slurry. The inhibitory effect of acidification on other microbes such as *Rhizobiales* and *Pirellulalles* could allow the preferential growth of other microbes such as LAB (Bastami et al., 2021).

4.3. Effect of acidification on the physical properties of the slurry

Acidification of slurry not only affects the chemical properties, it also influences the physical properties of the slurry to some extent. Lowering the slurry pH by adding acids increased the aggregation potential of the particles and led to higher particle size (pig slurry: 100–500 µm; cattle slurry: 250–1000 µm) as compared to non-acidified slurry which contains finer particles (Cocolo et al., 2016; Fangueiro et al., 2015; Hjorth et al., 2015; Regueiro et al., 2016). This could also be connected with the lowered viscosity of the acidified slurry which ultimately reduced the settling resistance of the particles in the slurry (Cocolo et al., 2016). It was reported that the slurry acidification also influences the particle surface charge. Based on the previous studies the particle's surface charge shifts more toward the positive side and that could be due to the less negative zeta-potential of the acidified slurry (Cocolo et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2012). Regarding the slurry dry matter contents previous studies presented contradictory results however the majority of the studies reported an increase in the dry matter (cattle slurry-un acidified: 5.95–15%, cattle slurry-acidified: 6.18–16%; pig slurry-un acidified: 1.5–7.25%, pig slurry-acidified: 1.9–7.85%) by acidification (Cocolo et al., 2016; Eriksen et al., 2008; Fangueiro et al., 2018; Kai et al., 2008;

Fig. 6. Average NH₃ and CH₄ mitigation potential of different acidic/acidifying agents used for slurry acidification. The average percentage mitigation calculated from the studies is summarised in Tables 1 and 2. Different shapes of points represent the scale of studies. Values in brackets represent the number of studies used to calculate the average. Error bars represent the standard error.

Pedersen et al., 2022).

5. Effect of acidification on NH₃ and GHG emissions from slurry

Research to evaluate the emission mitigation potential of slurry acidification has increased significantly in the recent past. The outcomes of the research so far showed the great potential of slurry acidification to overcome environmental pollution by reducing NH₃ and GHG emissions. It was observed that the emissions reduction potential strongly depends on the type of acid/acidifying agent. However, many other factors also influence the effectiveness of acidification. Fig. 6 shows the emission mitigation potential of different acidic/acidifying agents from cattle and pig slurry. The values used in Fig. 6 are collected from the studies summarised in Tables 1 and 2. We have critically reviewed the research conducted recently on slurry acidification in the sections below.

5.1. In house acidification

In-house acidification of slurry can reduce the terrestrial eutrophication potential by 71% and NH₃ emissions by 77 ± 11% (Sajeev et al., 2018; Ten Hoeve et al., 2016). Acidification of slurry with H₂SO₄ (pH < 6) by using treatment tanks reduces NH₃ emissions in-house by 44–71% from cattle and pig slurry storage facilities (Kai et al., 2008; Petersen et al., 2016). The addition of diluted acidic agents on the surface of slurry can also reduce the emissions significantly. For example, the outcomes of a study conducted by Juan et al., (2019) at laboratory scale showed that the application of diluted phosphoric acid (0.017 mol.L⁻¹; sow slurry (pH 8.0) and 0.4 mol.L⁻¹; cattle slurry (pH 7.01)) on the surface of the slurry reduced NH₃ emissions by 74% and 80% respectively as compared to non-acidified slurry. Similarly, in a laboratory study Zhang et al. (2021) reported a 98% reduction in NH₃ emissions in cattle housing by acidifying the slurry surface under the slatted floor. Subsequent storage of in-house acidified slurry reduced NH₃ emissions

by up to 22%. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2019) termed cattle slurry surface acidification a highly efficient technique for abatement of NH₃ emissions. This measure is only effective for a short period of time as the pH would soon start to increase again due to the buffer capacity because the effect of surface applied acid might not impact the pH of the slurry in the lower sections of the pit. However, further research is required on this aspect on a long term basis to better understand its feasibility and the effectiveness.

Retrofitting of acidification technologies is possible in existing pig and cattle barns. A 39% reduction in NH₃ emissions was reported by deploying a retrofitable system in pig barns to acidify the slurry, where concentrated H₂SO₄ (17.1 kg H₂SO₄ (96%) (m³ slurry)⁻¹, average pH 5.2) was used inside the barn during three fattening periods (Overmeyer et al., 2023).

Apart from NH₃ emissions, acidification of slurry also reduces GHG emissions. CH₄ is the most important GHG emitted from animal houses. Generally, the slurry in pigs and cattle houses stored in the pits under slatted floors where the anaerobic conditions are predominant (Dalby et al., 2021a, 2021b) and anaerobic microbes transform organic matter to CH₄ and CO₂. Lowering the pH of slurry by acidification inhibits the anaerobic methanogens and reduces CH₄ emissions (Latif et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2020). Around 50–92% reduction of CH₄ emissions was observed from pig houses where the slurry was acidified with H₂SO₄ to a pH below 6 (Dalby et al., 2022; Overmeyer et al., 2023; Vechi et al., 2022). Apart from lowering the pH of slurry, slurry temperature also an important factor that affects methanogens. Temperatures between 35 and 55°C favour methanogens and can increase methane production (Chen and Chang, 2020). Therefore, the effectiveness of CH₄ mitigation measures in the barn is pronounced through the higher temperatures inside the barn as compared to manure outside storage. For example, ~40% lower CH₄ emissions were reported from the acidified slurry (pH 4.9–5.1) in pig houses during spring season (15.5°C) as compared to the summer season (21.6°C). Along with acidification, keeping the temperature around 20°C and removing the slurry frequently from the

Fig. 7. (a) Relationship between H₂SO₄ dosage and slurry pH during manure storage (b) effect of slurry storage temperature and (c) slurry pH on NH₃ mitigation potential by acidification.

slurry pits can effectively reduce CH₄ emissions from pig and cattle housing (Dalby et al., 2023). Vecchi et al. (2022) highlighted the lower emissions from pig houses in spring and early summer due to emptying of slurry pits.

A couple of studies also measured N₂O emissions during in-house acidification. There was significant variability in the results as Spiëhs & Woodbury (2024) showed a reduction in N₂O emissions by acidifying the beef feedlot surface with alum and microbial inoculation. An increase in N₂O emissions was reported by Dalby et al. (2022) which is because of obvious reasons as they used HNO₃ for acidification. However, both studies were conducted at a laboratory scale and need further investigation to clearly understand the effect of acidification on N₂O emissions. Further research is needed keeping in mind different housing factors e.g., temperature, frequency of slurry removal, animal and human welfare and worker safety. A summary of emission mitigation through cattle and pig slurry acidification is given in Tables 1 and 2.

5.2. Acidification during slurry storage

Some sources consider acidification of slurry during storage more feasible than acidification in housing, probably because of infrastructure requirements (Larsson, 2018; Saue and Tamm, 2018). Lowering the pH of slurry during storage outside the animal housing could reduce NH₃ emissions by 58–99% and 72–99% from pig and cattle slurry respectively (El Bied et al., 2023; Fuchs et al., 2021; Lemes et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2022; Spiëhs and Woodbury, 2024; Wang et al., 2021). Similarly, inhibition of methanogens by slurry acidification during storage could reduce CH₄ emissions by 70–99% and 89–95% from pig and cattle slurry respectively (Ambrose et al., 2023a; Cong et al., 2023a; Dalby et al., 2022; Im et al., 2020, 2021). This variation in emission reduction could depend on various factors such as type of acid or acidifying agent, type of slurry, composition of slurry and initial pH of slurry, storage conditions and the frequency of acidification etc.

Both pig and cattle slurries differ in the composition hence require different amounts of acid or acidifying agents for the acidification to a required pH of 5.5. Dry matter content of the slurry is an important factor affecting the amount of acid. Higher amounts of H₂SO₄ (7%) and FeCl₃ (70%) were required to achieve the target pH of 5.5 of a cattle slurry with 7% dry matter content as compared to the cattle slurry with 4% dry matter (Kavanagh et al., 2019). Similarly, a 25% higher amount of H₂SO₄ was needed to attain the pH 5.5 of cattle slurry (dry matter 54.8 g/kg slurry) as compared to pig slurry (dry matter 15.3 g/kg slurry) (Regueiro et al., 2016b). The probable reasoning behind that is the association of higher VFA contents with slurries with higher dry matter contents (Kavanagh et al., 2019). In contrast to that, Finzi et al. (2024) reported the requirement of higher acid dosage (1.6–9.4 mL/kg) for pig slurries as compared to cattle slurries (0.8–5.3 mL/kg). It was also observed that the rise in pH after acidification was faster and higher for pig slurries as compared to cattle slurries. This is probably due to higher organic matter in cattle slurries leading to higher catabolic activity and CO₂ accumulation which helps keep the pH at low levels (Finzi et al., 2024; Petersen et al., 2012). Another reason for this could be the higher initial pH of pig slurries (6.7–8) as compared to cattle slurries (6.5–7.3). This variation in composition of slurries could affect the emission reduction potential during slurry acidification. However, more research is required to understand in detail the relationship between the dry matter contents, initial pH of the slurry and required acid dose to achieve the target pH.

Acid dose is another important factor which affects the reduction in the slurry pH to a target level and ultimately affecting the emission reduction potential of slurry acidification process. Generally, the acid dose has an indirect relationship with the slurry pH as seen in the Fig. 7a. Similarly, Kavanagh et al. (2021) evaluated the effect of different dosage of FeCl₃ on slurry pH and emission reduction. Addition of low amounts of FeCl₃ 0.3% and 0.9% reduce the pH initially but for a shorter period as the slurry pH rise again within few days courtesy of buffer capacity.

However, addition of higher amount of FeCl₃ 1.1% reduced the slurry pH for a longer period and ultimately reduced the CH₄ emissions significantly (~65%) while the lower level addition of FeCl₃ did not impact the emissions. Furthermore, similar effect on pH and emissions was observed with the addition of different dosage of H₂SO₄ and sulphur (1.2–6.0 kg H₂SO₄/m₃ slurry) (Ma et al., 2022; Maffia et al., 2020; Sokolov et al., 2021). Therefore, acid dosage which is good enough to reduce the pH for longer period should be added to effectively reduce the emissions.

Apart from slurry and acid specific parameters, conditions of slurry storage (e.g., storage temperature) also play an important role in determining the emission mitigation by slurry acidification (Fig. 7b). Temperature variation during slurry storage could influence the emissions (Zhang et al., 2021). Increase in temperature increased the microbial activity and could increase the emissions (Habtewold et al., 2018). According to Elsgaard et al. (2016) increase in the storage temperature from 15°C to 20°C increased the CH₄ production by 81%. However, cooling of slurry during storage reduced the NH₃ and CH₄ emissions more than 60% (Hilgert et al., 2022; Myczko et al., 2007). In addition, Slurry storage temperature could influence the efficiency of acidification in reducing the emissions. For example, Storage of acidified slurry at 20°C showed higher emission reduction as compared to the same acidified slurry stored at 25°C and 30°C (Im et al., 2020). Analysis of temperature data from the collected studies showed that increase in the temperature of the manure reduce the NH₃ reduction percentage (Fig. 7b). However, there is a huge variability in the outcomes of different studies which could be due to the type of storage system, type of acidic/acidifying agent, amount of acidic/acidifying agents, composition of slurry used in different studies, initial pH of slurry, dry matter/total solid contents and the type of study, but the general trend supports this fact. Furthermore, Managing the slurry storage temperature to lower level reduced the amount of acid (1/3rd) required to effectively mitigate the emissions because at lower storage temperature the mild acidified slurry (pH 6.5–7.0) could reduce the emissions as much as the highly acidified slurry (Im et al., 2020). Similarly, acidified slurries stored under warm conditions showed a quicker increase in pH (from pH 5.7 to 7.0 in 25 days) as compared to slurry stored in cold conditions (from pH 5.5 to 7.0 in around 60 days) (Adamsen et al., 2021). Therefore, improving the slurry storage conditions along with manure management techniques e.g., acidification is important to achieve the full emission reduction potential.

During the literature review it was observed that most of the research on this technique is still at base level. To clearly understand the effectiveness of acidification in reducing the emission of pollutants and hazardous gases, more pilot scale studies are required.

Consideration of long term impacts of slurry acidification is important. Application of acidified slurry to soil could reduce NH₃ emissions by 45–97% as compared to conventional slurry (Ellersiek and Olf, 2024; Keskinen et al., 2022; Langley-Randall et al., 2024; Pedersen et al., 2022; Wagner et al., 2021). In addition, it could improve apparent nitrogen recovery (65%) and dry matter yield (29–40%) and grain yield (20%) of crops (Keskinen et al., 2022; Loide et al., 2020). However, outcomes on N₂O emissions are variable as some of the studies showed reduction in N₂O emissions (48.7–71.8%) while some showed an increase in N₂O emissions (36%) (Malique et al., 2021; Park et al., 2018). Similarly, Langley-Randall et al. (2024) reported non-significant effect of acidified slurry application to soil on N₂O emissions as compared to unacidified slurry. Furthermore, slurry acidification could increase non-methane volatile organic compounds by 202% and 17% after storage and field acidification respectively (Pedersen et al., 2022). To understand the effect of acidified slurry on GHG emissions further research is required as its impact on CH₄ and N₂O is not fully clear. Future research should also focus on key variables impacting the GHG emissions from soils where acidified slurry is applied.

6. Potential combination of acidification with other manure treatment technologies

It is always better to align the emission reduction techniques with the ongoing management practices at farms. An example of this is the study conducted by Mendes et al. (2017), they reported through a modelling approach that combining manure acidification in manure pits (pH 5–6.5) with floor scrapping could reduce NH₃ emissions up to 44–49%. Below are discussed the potential combinations of other manure management practices with slurry acidification.

6.1. Solid-Liquid separation

As mentioned above the acidification increased the particle size of the slurries, which leads to an increase in the solid fraction after solid-liquid separation. However, there is no consensus about this effect as some of the researchers also reported contradictory results. We have summarised here both cases with the given justification by the researchers. The increase in solid fraction by acidification could depend on the acid/acidifying agent as the solid fraction (particles > 100 µm) was higher with alum as compared to H₂SO₄ (Regueiro et al., 2016). Similarly, Regueiro et al. (2016) reported that slurry acidification before solid-liquid separation increased the acidified solid fraction from 3–4% as compared to non-acidified slurry (for reasoning see Section 4.3). In contrary to that, reduction in the solid fraction after solid-liquid separation of the acidified slurry was also reported (Cocolo et al., 2016; Sommer et al., 2015). An increase in the particle size after acidification increased the flow rate of liquid fraction during solid-liquid separation and there would be less time for the settlement of finer particles which ultimately ended up in the liquid fraction and lowered the separated solid fraction (Cocolo et al., 2016). Acidification of slurry before separation reduced the dry matter separation index by 50% and 35% for screw press and decanter centrifuge techniques respectively (Cocolo et al., 2016). Solid fraction of acidified slurry after solid-liquid separation possesses lower concentrations of P, S, N, volatile solids, and ash as compared to the liquid fraction possibly due to the quicker dewatering process of acidified slurry (Cocolo et al., 2016, 2013; Fangueiro et al., 2015). There is no consensus about the concentration of divalent cations such as copper and Zn. Some researchers reported higher concentrations of Cu and Zn in the liquid fraction with the reasoning of higher solubility of such elements due to acidification (Cocolo et al., 2013; Fangueiro et al., 2009) while others reported higher concentrations of these cations in the solid fractions stating a strong bonding/attachment of these cations to the particulate matter (Cocolo et al., 2016; Regueiro et al., 2016a; Sommer et al., 2015).

Separation of solid fraction and the distribution of nutrients and other organic and inorganic components between the solid and liquid fraction could depend on the type of acid, type of slurry, slurry composition, solid-liquid separation technique, and the flow rate during solid-liquid separation. Further research is needed to better understand the compatibility of both of these technologies.

6.2. Anaerobic digestion

Generally, it is reported that CH₄ yield during anaerobic digestion (AD) is lower from the acidified slurry as compared to the non-acidified slurry (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2023). This is due to the inhibition of microbial activities due to lower pH (Huang et al., 2018) or could be due to the inhibition caused by sulphur (Habtewold et al., 2018). However, no difference in CH₄ yield was observed from the acidified solid fraction of the slurry during AD (Sutaryo et al., 2013), probably because of low sulphate and volatile fatty acid contents in the solid fraction. On the other hand, it was reported that the co-digestion of acidified manure along with non-acidified manure increased the CH₄ yield (Fangueiro et al., 2015; Moset et al., 2016, 2012; Moset et al., 2012). It was stated that adding 10% of the acidified manure during AD could increase the

CH₄ yield up to 10–20%. This could be due to increased degradation of organic matter. Co-digestion of acidified and non-acidified manure seems a feasible option until the balance between the readily biodegradable compounds and the increased sulphur contents is maintained (Fangueiro et al., 2015; Moset et al., 2012). Alternatively, the use of energy crops as a buffer substrate during the AD of the acidified slurry could be a good option because an animal farm could either have acidified slurry or raw slurry. This could be a good starting point for future research. Furthermore, AD of the bio-acidified slurry by using whey increased the methane yield from 33–53% as compared to non-acidified slurry (Gioelli et al., 2022). This could be due to higher butyric acid production during AD of the bio-acidified slurry which has a higher metabolization rate (Calero et al., 2018). Further research is still required to evaluate the feasibility and economic aspects of this technique on a larger scale.

6.3. Composting

Nitrogen volatilization during the composting of solid manure is the limitation of this treatment technology as it affects the nutrient balance of the end product (Lim et al., 2017). The process of volatilization mainly depends on the pH and the temperature of the compost. Acidification of raw solid manure before composting showed encouraging results in reducing N emissions. In recent research, it was reported that the addition of elemental sulphur at the rate of 1.4 g.kg⁻¹ to the solid manure during composting significantly reduced the manure pH (6.85) and increased the NH₄⁺ contents (83.1%) as compared to the control treatment (pH 9.04) (Holatko et al., 2022). Similarly, Cao et al. (2020) stated that composting of acidified poultry manure (pH 6.0) reduced GHG emissions (9.6%) and NH₃ emissions (21.3%). This increase in the NH₄⁺ contents and reduction in the emissions is because of the reduced organic matter decomposition/inhibition of biological oxidation due to low pH and temperature (Cao et al., 2020). Similar results were also reported by adding acidified saw dust during the composting of sewage sludge. It was stated that regulation of pH 5.51–6.48 reduced the N losses from 24.8% to 44.7% and reduced NH₃ emissions up to 52.1% as compared to control (Li and Li, 2015), and no adverse effect on the microbial activity and organic matter degradation was found. Similar results were also reported in other studies (Gu et al., 2011; Kithome et al., 1999; Tran et al., 2011).

6.4. Frequent removal of slurry

In animal housing, slurry is generally stored in pits before transferring it to outside storage. In house storage of slurry can increase the emissions in the barn because the temperature inside the barns is higher as compared to outside storage (Philippe and Nicks, 2015). The volume of slurry inside the barns can be reduced by transferring slurry frequently to the outside storages. There are different systems to remove slurry frequently e.g., slanted walls, vacuum system, back flushing and scrapers (Santonja et al., 2017). Slurry removal frequency and slurry removal efficiency are the main factors affecting the efficiency of this process (Ambrose et al., 2023b). According to Philippe and Nicks (2015) CH₄ mitigation should increase by more frequent slurry removal. In the case of pig production, emptying slurry pits two to three times per week reduced CH₄ emissions by more than 80% as compared to control conditions (Ambrose et al., 2023b; Dalby et al., 2023). One of the reasons behind these reduced CH₄ emissions could be reduced dependency of methane emission on variation in slurry temperature due to increased slurry removal frequency and the reduced activity of specific methanogens (Feng et al., 2022). Combining slurry acidification with frequent slurry removal could be an effective strategy to reduce emissions from animal housing and storage. Frequent removal of slurry (once a week or two to three times a week as used in the mentioned studies) reduced net CH₄ emissions (housing and storage emissions) by 53–83% in winter and 18–41% in summer and combined with acidification reduced net CH₄

emissions by more than 90% (Dalby et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2023).

Efficiency of slurry removal is an important factor because the amount of slurry left in the pits (residual slurry) is also influenced by removal frequency. The leftover slurry in the pits can influence CH₄ emissions in the next cycle. Higher methanogenic activity in the residual slurry can accelerate the CH₄ emission process in the newly added slurry (Dalby et al., 2021b). Acidification of residual slurry left in the pits can reduce emissions in the next cycle. According to Sokolov et al. (2020) NH₃ and CH₄ emissions were reduced by 38% and 23% by acidifying the residual slurry respectively. Therefore combining these manure management practices presents greater potential to reduce the emissions from animal housing and storage.

7. Practicality and challenges in the implementation of slurry acidification

It is evident from the literature that slurry acidification has a significant impact on NH₃ and CH₄ emissions. However, the applicability of this technique at the national level or even at the farm scale is not so common in the majority of countries. Different factors are impeding the application of slurry acidification, these factors also vary according to the individual countries. While there are some common factors e.g., farm infrastructure, cost-intensive, government regulations, acid supply, safety concerns, etc. Denmark is a country where this technique is widely implemented at a national level (Mikkelsen and Nyord, 2019; Pedersen et al., 2022). The design of slurry storage tanks in Denmark makes slurry acidification possible, while in some other countries, there are regulations regarding the size and design of slurry storage tanks (Rodhe et al., 2017). Normally, a bigger volume of storage tanks is required to make it practically beneficial and the farmers are not willing to invest in that (Rodhe et al., 2017). There is also a risk of the erosion of concrete in the current storage tanks showing that the current infrastructure from housing to storage is outdated in terms of the implementation of manure acidification. On the other hand, in-house acidification can only be possible by modifying the design of animal houses or re-constructing new houses with a slurry acidification system, which rather seems impractical. Current animal houses in most countries are not suitable for the implementation of acidification techniques. One way to steer the minds of the farmers in that direction could be to provide subsidies. As we mentioned above, the results of a survey-based study among the farmers in Germany showed that about 81 % of the farmers were ready to take the initiative if subsidies are provided, and that too depends on the ultimate benefits e.g., reduction in the environmental impact, increasing the fertilizer value of slurry, reducing the nitrogen input in the croplands, etc. (Ten Hove et al., 2016; Thiermann and Latacz-Lohmann, 2022). At the current stage with existing housing infrastructure, the safety of workers and animals is also a major concern as the production of harmful gases can lead to hazardous effects on living beings. However, the handling of the acid is no more a concern as the acidification system implemented in Denmark is designed in a way to avoid the risks that could occur during acid handling (Jacobsen, 2015). Apart from the regulatory and infrastructure-related factors, other factors such as over-fertilization of sulphur through the application of acidified slurry (H₂SO₄ acidified) in the soil (Bittman et al., 2014) could also impact the decision-making in favour of this technique. The excessive sulphur could leach down to the underground water in the form of sulphate ions; particularly in calcium-poor soils (Loide et al., 2020). To avoid this issue the acidification of slurry by using organic acids or other biological or organic materials could be done. However further research is needed to understand the feasibility, economics, and practicality of such alternative acidic/acidifying agents.

8. Advancements in the research related to slurry acidification

Slurry acidification is a highly effective emission mitigation strategy throughout the manure management chain. Basic research on slurry

acidification started long ago, however, this mitigation strategy came under the lens since the start of its practical application in some of the countries e.g., Denmark. Several inorganic acids, salts, and sugars have been tested to reduce the pH of slurry and the majority of those studies were summarised by Fanguero and co-authors in 2015 (Fanguero et al., 2015). Since then a significant number of studies have been published not only focusing on mineral acids and salts but also on organic acids, microbial inoculations, and bio-waste materials as acidifying agents. Based on the recent literature we concluded some new findings such as:

- i. Emission mitigation range for NH₃ and CH₄ is provided for different acid/acidifying agents by keeping in mind the slurry type and the scale of study.
- ii. Relationship of H₂SO₄ dosage with pig and cattle slurry is presented.
- iii. Recent developments regarding the potential combination of acidification with other manure management practices at housing storage level are discussed.

However, the research regarding innovative bio-materials, bio-wastes, and microbial inoculations is still at a very basic level. Further research is required to better understand the feasibility and practicality of such materials at a large scale.

9. Conclusion

Slurry acidification is a successful method for reducing NH₃ and GHG emissions both in housing and during storage. Based on the recently published literature it can be concluded that apart from the mineral acids acidifying agents such as organic acids, bio-waste materials, and microbial inoculations could be used as an alternative to mineral acids to reduce environmental pollution. However, further research is required to understand their feasibility, practicality, and economic aspects. Recent literature further confirms the synergistic role of slurry acidification with other manure management techniques such as anaerobic digestion, solid-liquid separation, and composting and frequent manure removal to increase the emission reduction potential. It is also concluded that the major part of research related to slurry acidification focused on the manure storage stage, while still limited studies are available regarding in-house slurry acidification. Further research on that aspect is required to understand the feasibility of slurry acidification considering the available infrastructure (e.g., housing systems). Along with that, a major part of the research on manure acidification was carried out at a laboratory scale, while more research at a pilot or commercial scale is required for further understanding and implementation at the farm scale. In addition, knowledge gaps still exist about potential pollution-swapping effects. Slurry acidification is successfully operational in Denmark, thus, it is reasonable to assume that the technique can be used in many other countries. However, a lack of implementation is still observed in many countries, and the reasons for this need to be understood to overcome potential implementation barriers. A diverse range of acids/acidifying agents tested in the recent studies (sugars, biowaste materials, salts etc.) suggested a greater potential to implement slurry acidification technique in storage as well as in animal houses without impacting the animals and workers health. The use of environment friendly materials might also reduce the infrastructural changes in animal houses to implement the acidification technique. Future studies should also focus on evaluating the important components of slurry influencing the acidification efficiency and the dose of acid required to reach the target pH. There is no doubt in effectiveness of acidification in reducing emissions from livestock systems. However, the implementation of slurry acidification at a larger scale still depends on the regulations in different countries and the farmer's decision and ability to invest to change the infrastructure. Slurry acidification holds large potentials to reduce the environmental impact of livestock production.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wajid Umar: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Chari Vandenburg:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Elio Dinuccio:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Dong Hongmin:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Barbara Amon:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the European Union Horizon Europe Innovation program [Grant Agreement No. 101081858], titled “ECO-NUTRI: Innovative concepts and technologies for Ecologically sustainable Nutrient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water and air”.

Data availability

All the data used is presented in the manuscript in Table 1.

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